

AccessAfrica Guidelines on Post-Trial Access for International Clinical Trials in Sub-Saharan Africa

Authors: Rosemarie Bernabe, Gudina Terefe Tucho

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Contributors:

Ahmed Abdallah, Benjamin Watyaba, Bernard Kikaire, Beth Mutumba, Christopher Ddamulira, Cynthia Khamala Wangamati, David Marenga, David Walusimbi, Debora Bade, Diana Kesi Nakitto, Diribe Makonene Kumsa, Ewanat Gebrehanna, Haile Michael Bizuneh, Helen Ndagije, Hellen Opolot, Irene Semakula, Jean Baptiste Nyandwi, Joyce Batera, Lillian Omutoko, Keziah Chanyisa Khayadi Dash, Marcelline Djuidje, Martha Zewdie, Mary Mayige, Mekonnen Teferi, Melat Gebremedhin, Mike Campbell, Nassim Kyakuwa, Nuraan Fakier, Obadia Bishoge, Peter Kitooke, Rose Naluwuge, Shereen Dawkins Cox, Shija Kuhumba, Sia Malekia, Telahun Teka, Violet Naanyu, Vivian Nchanchou Mbanya, Winfred Badanga, Yemisrach Zewdie Seralegne

(in case we missed out on a contributor, please send email to Rosemarie Bernabe, rdbernab@uio.no)

AccessAfrica Guidelines on Post-Trial Access for International Clinical Trials in Sub-Saharan Africa

Following the CIOMS definition of post-trial access (PTA) as the obligation of sponsors and researchers -- in coordination with the host government and other relevant stakeholders including the community and the research ethics committees -- “to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population or community in which the research is carried out”;

Acknowledging that there are several forms of benefit-sharing and that post-trial responsibilities may extend beyond PTA, with the latter being an element of the former;

Recognizing that PTA must be understood alongside the ethical responsibility for responsiveness;

Asserting that PTA is a requirement born from distributive justice, beneficence, respect for persons, reciprocity, solidarity, and fairness;

Asserting that PTA refers access to both knowledge in the form of clinical trial results and intervention, if any, and in the case the latter, ensuring that associated medical care and infrastructure are in place;

Asserting that PTA has both societal and individual dimensions, with the former expressed in terms of access responsibilities to the community and/or the population and the latter as adaptable to individual needs;

Asserting that just health is a multi-stakeholder and a multi-national responsibility, not solely of individual SSA nations;

Asserting that the obligation for PTA is strongest in regions where overall access to health is low;

Asserting that PTA obligations in low and middle-income countries, at least from the societal dimension, are inalienable and are not reducible to individual contractual obligations;

Agreeing with the *UN Human Rights Guidelines for Pharmaceutical Companies to Access to Medicines* that the primary responsibility to health belongs to States;

Agreeing with the UN Human Rights Guidelines for Pharmaceutical Companies in Relation to Access to Medicines that central to the societal mission of pharmaceutical companies is enhancing access to medicines;

The following are the principles governing PTA in clinical trials:

1. PTA arrangements must be included in the planning of clinical trials. The provision of PTA must be the standard. Any deviation from the standard must have an ethically justifiable reason approved by the ethics committee.
2. PTA refers to access to both knowledge and intervention, if any, by the research participants and the community and/or host country.
3. PTA is a multi-stakeholder responsibility. Provision arrangements must be led by the sponsor and/or the principal investigator in close collaboration with the research ethics committees, clinical trial regulators, and the community. To ensure that PTA benefits individuals, the community, and the host country, planning and execution must include all relevant stakeholders.
4. To best serve the interests of participants and the community, the planning and details of post-trial arrangements must be continuously reconsidered by the sponsor and the principal investigator throughout the study, in close collaboration with the community. Changes to PTA plans must be sent to the research ethics committee for approval.
5. PTA arrangements should include access to relevant study findings for participants, the community, the host country, and the general public. Clinical trials must provide this knowledge to the host country's stakeholders efficiently, facilitating its use for community benefits. Dissemination of knowledge should target not only the scientific community but also the general public in the host country, ensuring widespread accessibility.
6. If therapeutic products meant for commercial distribution (such as investigational medicinal products or medical devices) are involved in the

trials, research participants who still need the intervention and community and/or host country access to the therapeutic intervention must also be provided.

7. PTA provision of therapeutic products ranges from cost-free provision to research participants to availability and accessibility of the product for the community and/or host country. The sponsor, in cooperation with the community and the host country, must also ensure that the associated medical care and infrastructure are in place.
8. The provision of PTA to individual participants will be dependent on the risk-benefit profile of the investigational product in comparison with standard. PTA for individual participants lasts until the therapeutic product is authorized, marketed, and accessible in the host country; when the product's authorization application has been rejected; or even before marketing authorization procedures if, for example, the usefulness of the investigational medicinal product for the individual participant ceases. The plans for transition from individual PTA to sourcing the appropriate medicinal product from the national healthcare system must be clearly stipulated in the clinical trial's PTA plans.
9. To ensure PTA for the community/host country, the PTA plan must include provisions for a formal agreement between the sponsor and the host country that the sponsor will apply for marketing authorization for the therapeutic product, once proven safe and effective, and will market the product in the host country within an agreed period not exceeding five years from the last pivotal clinical trial. This agreement must also cover the pricing mechanism for the therapeutic product. Pricing must be equitable. Equity must be determined by the sponsors and the principal investigator, with the explicit agreement of the research ethics committee and relevant host country regulators. It must be based on considerations including the national healthcare system of the host country, the gravity and magnitude of the need for the intervention, the ability of the citizens to pay, and other considerations of equity.

Table 1: PTA Responsibilities of the different stakeholders (note: **x in red specifies the main responsible stakeholder/s)**

		Sponsor	Principal investigator	REC (Host country and the	Host community	Regulators (Host country)
	PRE-CLINICAL TRIAL					
1	Identify whether the study intervention is responsive to the needs of the host community	x	x		x	
2	Identify what should be provided to the participants and the community/host country at the end of the trial. Note that all clinical trials are required to disseminate knowledge gained from the study.	x	x		x	
3	Identify resources needed and the resources available to provide PTA	x	x		x	
4	With regard to PTA for research participants, if applicable, set out and agree on the protocol for the transition from the experimental therapeutic intervention to a medicinal product via the national healthcare system.	x	x			x
5	For reasons related to the safety of the research participants, if necessary and applicable, indicate criteria for exclusion in PTA.	x	x			
6	Indicate criteria for ending of PTA.	x	x		x	

7	With regard to PTA for the community/host country, set out and agree on the terms of marketing the medicinal product, when proven safe and effective, in the host country. The terms should include when and at what cost the product will be made available and accessible at the host country.	X	X			X
8	Draft the PTA plans, including the logistics and practical plans for provision, and agreements to be submitted to the REC approval. PTA provisions relevant to the research participants must also be included in the informed consent process and documents.	X	X	X	X	
9	Deliberate on the ethical acceptability of the PTA plans in accordance with the principles set forth in this guidance document.			X		
	DURING THE CLINICAL TRIAL					
10	Based on interim results of efficacy and safety, adapt the PTA plans and agreements in consultation with all the relevant stakeholders. Updated PTA plans, together with the reasons for the changes made, must be submitted to the REC for approval.	X	X		X	
11	Evaluate the updated PTA plans and other relevant documents such as validity of current informed consent documents.			X		
12	If there are changes to the PTA plans for research participants, updating of the participants' informed consent could be required by the research ethics committee.	X	X	X		

	AT THE END OF TRIAL					
13	Finalize PTA agreements based on the most recent PTA plan.	X	X	X	X	X
14	Before the end of their participation in the trial, brief the research participants using the most recent PTA information. Inform them about the PTA they can expect after the trial, the duration of this access, the transition process, and other relevant practical details.	X	X			
15	Ensure accessibility of relevant study findings for participants, the community, the host country, and the general public.	X	X			
16	Ensure that logistics are in place for the implementation of PTA for both research participants and the community/host country.	X	X		X	X
17	Monitor proper implementation of PTA.			X		X